

Purification and characterization of an acid protease produced by a mutant strain of *Aspergillus niger*

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Abstract : *Aspergillus niger*, isolated from the soil, secretes an acidic protease into the medium on exposure to UV-irradiation for 1, 2, 3, h, the organism was mutated and the mutants thus obtained were screened for maximum protease production. This extracellular protease was purified to apparent homogeneity by chromatography on DEAE-cellulose. Homogeneity was ascribed by electrophoresis. The molecular weight, as determined by SDS-PAGE was 39800 daltons. This protease has an optimum activity at a pH of 6.0 and temperature of 37 °C. It is inhibited by metal ions like Cu^{2+} but is active in the presence of metal ions like Mn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} .

Keywords : Acid protease, mutant strain, *Aspergillus niger*.

Introduction

Proteases are one of the most important groups of enzymes constituting about two-thirds of the total industrial enzymes marked^{1,2}. The major applications are in the food, pharmaceutical and detergent industries. Alkaline proteases are mostly used is enzyme containing detergent powders and have minor uses in food processing e.g. chill proofing of beer and production of protein hydrolysate³⁻⁵.

Screening and development of high yielding mutant strain : Screening of the microbe was done by serial dilution method and 321 pure colonies were separated out of which the maximum protease producing strain (36.95 u/ml) was isolated and made ready for mutation.

UV rays treatment : To carry out mutational studies the isolated fungal colony was transferred to czapekdox agar slants and incubated at 32 °C for 6 days for sufficient mycelia formation. The spore suspension was taken in a petridish (5 cm diameter) and were exposed to UV-irradiation (15 W) for 1, 2 and 3 h. The treated spores were plated on czapekdox plates which were incubated at 32 °C for 6 days. Selected colonies were transferred to czapekdox agar slants and stored at 4 °C after 6 days incubation at 32 °C. Using these mutant strains fermenta-

tions were carried out and the highest protease producing strain was isolated. About 830 colonies were isolated after mutation and out of these mutants only one strain *Aspergillus niger* AB775 produced higher amount of protease (40.91 u/ml) than the parent strain (36.95 u/ml).

Method of assay of protease activity : After fermentation mycelium was separated from the fermentation medium by filtration through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and the clear filtrate was assayed for protease activity. The enzyme activity was determined by the method of Myers and Ahearn¹⁶. Reaction mixture containing 0.5 ml culture filtrate, 0.5 ml citrate buffer (pH 6.0) and 1.0 ml of 1% casein (Hammerstein) solution dissolved in citrate buffer was incubated at 35 °C for 20 min. The reaction was stopped by adding 4 ml of 5% trichloroacetic acid (TCA). After 1 h the solution was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. One ml of this filtrate was mixed with 5 ml of 0.04 (M) Na_2CO_3 solution to which 0.5 ml of phenol reagent was added. The optical density was measured at 660 nm after 10 min. In blank TCA was added to the incubation mixture at time zero. Amount of tyrosine liberated at 660 nm was calculated by comparing.

Acid proteases play an important role in meat tenderization and in the production of fermented food by molds

from soyabean, rice and other cereals^{1,6}. They are also used in the baking industry for the modification of wheat proteins in bread doughs and in the dairy industry for clotting of milk to manufacture cheese⁷.

Acid proteases of commercial importance are prepared exclusively from fungal sources and they are all extracellular in nature. Work has already been done on the microbial production and purification of protease from different sources like *Enterococcus faecalis*⁸, *Candida huinicola*⁹, *Rhizopus oryzae*¹⁰, *Aspergillus oryzae*¹¹, *Vigna umbellata*¹², *Agkistroden piscivorus*¹³, *Aeromonas proteolytica*¹⁴ and *Euphasia superba*¹⁵.

The present work reports the production, purification and characterization of an extracellular acid protease secreted by a mutant strain of *Aspergillus niger*.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism and cultural conditions *Aspergillus niger*, isolated from the soil was used for mutational studies. After exposure to UV-irradiations (15 W) for 1, 2 and 3 h a mutant strain of *Aspergillus niger* was isolated which gave a better yield of acid protease. This mutant strain was designated as *Aspergillus niger* AB₇₇₅ and was maintained on czapekdox agar medium. For protease production this *Aspergillus niger* AB₇₇₅ was inoculated into a fermentation medium (FM) containing NaNO₃, 0.2%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1%; KCl, 0.05% and MgCl₂, 0.025% (initial pH 6.0) in 100 ml distilled water in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer conical flask 2.0%. Glucose was added aseptically to the fermentation medium after sterilization. Shake culture fermentation was adopted for protease production with rotational speed of 150 r.p.m. Duration of fermentation was 9 days at 32 °C the values with that of a standard plot of tyrosine. Each value was divided by 20 to get the amount liberated per minute. One unit of enzyme activity was defined as the amount of enzyme liberating 1 µg. Tyrosine per minute under the defined conditions¹⁷.

Purification of the protease : The cell free culture supernatant obtained after filtration was concentrated on a rotary evaporator at 37 °C and then dialysed against 0.1 (M) phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) at 37 °C with 3–4 changes over 24 h. 4 ml of this dialysed solution (pH 7.0) was loaded onto a DEAE-cellulose column (63 mm × 14 mm). The column was first eluted with 0.01 (M) phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) and then stepwise NaCl gradient of

0.025 (M), 0.05 (M), 0.1 (M), 0.25 (M) and 0.5 (M) solutions was applied. 5 ml fractions were collected at room temperature and they were monitored at 280 nm to evaluate their protein content. Only the peak fractions were checked for protease activity by Folin-Phenol method¹⁶. 7.5% gel was used for polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis¹⁸. To confirm the homogeneity of the fractions obtained from the DEAE-cellulose column. 10% gel was used during SDS-PAGE analysis¹⁹ in the presence of β-mercapto ethanol to ascertain the molecular weight of the protease purified. Molecular weight markers that were used for molecular weight determination in SDS-PAGE are BSA (66000 daltons), Trypsin (22000 daltons) and Soyabean Trypsin Inhibitor (20000 daltons).

The molecular weights were plotted against relative mobility to ascertain the molecular weight of the enzyme. In both native and SDS – gel electrophoresis silver nitrate strain of proteins was performed by the method of Way *et al.*²⁰.

pH/Temperature optima of the protease : The pH optima of the protease was determined by measuring the activity in citrate buffer at pH ranging from 3.0 to 10.0.

The temperature optima was determined by incubating the protease in citrate buffer (pH 6.0) for 20 min at 6 °C, 10 °C, 18 °C, 30 °C, 45 °C, 50 °C, 55 °C and 65 °C. These samples were then used to measure the effect of temperature on proteolytic activity using casein as substrate by the method described above.

Effect of metal ions : Effect of some metal ions (listed in Table 2) on protease activity was determined by pre-incubating the purified enzyme with 5 nM each of chlorides of Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ba²⁺, Ca²⁺ and Cu²⁺ before assaying the enzyme activity.

Results and discussion

Purification of the protease : Because of its extracellular nature, the crude protease was obtained by filtration through cottonwool from the fermentation broth. Crude extract of the enzyme had a specific activity of 0.589 and after dialysis against 0.1 (M) phosphate buffer (pH 7.2), it was purified by 1.8 folds.

Five peaks were obtained from the ion-exchange column on DEAE-cellulose of which the last one P₅ which was eluted at a molarity of 0.5 (M) NaCl showed protease

activity. Three hundred fold purification was achieved by this process (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Ion exchange chromatography on a DEAE-cellulose column.

The column (63 mm × 14 mm) of DEAE-cellulose was equilibrated with 0.01 (M) phosphate buffers (pH 7.2). 4 ml of the dialysed solution from the previous step was applied to this column. Elution was performed with a stepwise gradient with 20 ml each of 0.025 (M), 0.05 (M), 0.1 (M), 0.25 (M) and 0.5 (M) NaCl solution. The eluant was monitored spectrophotometrically at 280 nm (○). Protease activity was measured at 660 nm (□).

On 7.5% PAGE of the crude enzyme produced two bands whereas P₅ produced a single band indicating the homogeneous nature of the enzyme (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. SDS polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of the crude extract, (NH₄)₂SO₄ fraction and DEAE-cellulose column fraction.

In reduced condition (SDS-PAGE) with β-mercapto ethanol P₅ also produced a single band. SDS-molecular weight was calculated to be 39800 daltons (Fig. 3).

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Lanes 3, 4 and 5 – Purified protease (single band) from P₅ fraction of DEAE – Cellulose Ion Exchange Column Chromatography

Lane 6 – Soybean Trypsin Inhibitor (20100 daltons)

Lane 9 – Bovine Serum Albumin (68000 daltons)

Lane 10 – Trypsin (22000 daltons)

Fig. 3. SDS-PAGE of the purified acid protease from *Aspergillus niger* AB₇₇₅ along with some standard molecular weight markers.

Typical procedure of the purification is described in Table 1.

Table 1. Purification steps of the protease produced by *Aspergillus niger* AB₇₇₅

Purification steps	Total protein (mg)	Total activity (units)	Specific activity (units/mg)
Crude extract	69.45	40.91	0.589
Dialysed extract	9.49	105.50	11.116
DEAE-cellulose column fraction	0.42	76.80	182.87

Table 1 indicates that the purified protein shows 300 folds increase in specific activity.

Characteristics of the protease : The protease was active at temperatures ranging from 18 °C to 45 °C. Actively increase from 6 °C and reaches a maximum at 37 °C and then it decreases to a minimum at 65 °C. Fig. 4 shows the temperature dependency of the enzyme activity.

Fig. 4. Relation between enzyme activity and temperature.

Again, the enzyme exhibited activity over a broad range of pH (3 to 10) with an optimum at pH 6.0. Fig. 5 show the pH dependency of the enzyme activity.

Fig. 5. Relation between enzyme activity and pH.

Effect of metal ions : The effect of different metal ions on protease activity is listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of some metal ions on the activity of protease secreted by *Aspergillus niger* AB₇₇₅

Metal ions	Concentration (mM)	Protease activity (units/ml)
Mn ²⁺	5	184.00
Mg ²⁺	5	109.00
Zn ²⁺	5	59.39
Ca ²⁺	5	63.35
Ba ²⁺	5	52.75
Cu ²⁺	5	3.95

It is evident from the above mentioned table that metal ion like Cu²⁺ inhibits protease activity (3.95 units/ml against a control of 48.83 units/ml). On the other hand, protease activity is increased in the presence of metal ions like Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺ and Zn²⁺ with an optimum activity of 184 units/ml in presence of Mn²⁺.

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